

THE CLINICAL IMPACT OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE ON COMPLICATIONS IN THE CENTRAL NERVOUS SYSTEM

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Abstract. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) impairs interactions with other organs, with the interaction between the kidneys and the heart being the most extensively studied. However, there is increasing evidence for a link between renal dysfunction and disorders of the central nervous system. In epidemiological studies.

Keywords: chronic kidney disease, neurological complications, uremic neuropathy, uremic encephalopathy, cognitive dysfunction, peripheral neuropathy, autonomic neuropathy

Introduction. CKD is associated with a high prevalence of neurological complications such as cerebrovascular disorders, movement disorders, cognitive impairment and depression. In addition to traditional cardiovascular risk factors (such as diabetes, inflammation, hypertension and dyslipidaemia), non-traditional risk factors associated with renal damage (such as uremic toxins) may predispose patients with CKD to neurological disorders. There is increasing evidence that uremic toxins, such as indoxyl sulphate, have neurotoxic effects. A better understanding of the factors responsible for the increased prevalence of neurological disorders in patients with CKD may contribute to the development of new therapies.

Patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) are prone to various neurological complications, affecting both the central and peripheral nervous system. The etiology may be due to primary kidney disease or to comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus, which can cause damage to several organs in the body. Early detection and treatment of these conditions is vital to reduce the severity of symptoms in patients with these neurological manifestations. Central nervous system: More broadly, as described by Rengen et al, CNS manifestations can be classified into two main categories: those affecting the vascular system and others that are neurodegenerative causes. The vascular component is associated with traditional cardiovascular risk factors, including diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension, hypercholesterolaemia, smoking and old age.

Non-traditional risk factors are higher in patients with CKD and include elevated calcium and phosphate levels, hyperhomocysteinaemia, inflammation and oxidative stress, leading to accelerated atherosclerosis and endothelial dysfunction. There is a high prevalence of cardiovascular disease due to microbleeds and white matter brain disease in patients on dialysis. Neurodegenerative causes have been linked to uremic toxins, especially indoxyl sulphate, p-cresyl sulphate, uric acid, interleukin (IL)-1beta. It has also been suggested that cystatin-C may lead to amyloid deposition. Anaemia and hyperparathyroidism have been attributed to neurocognitive impairment as a result of reduced oxygen delivery and parathyroid hormone (PTH) impeding neurotransmission to the CNS as a result of increased calcium levels in the brain, respectively. Interestingly, treatment with erythropoietin stimulating drugs (ESA) increases the risk of stroke. Intermittent haemodynamic shifts observed during dialysis have been shown to cause perfusion-related brain damage, although 'dialysis dementia', which was seen in an earlier era due to aluminium exposure, is now rare. The prevalence of cognitive decline in these patients is estimated to be as high as 60%. The retention of metabolites associated with uremia was thought to be the main cause of 'uremic encephalopathy'. Methylguanidine, guanidine, guanidinoacetic acid and even creatinine have been shown to cause seizures in animal experiments. Elevated blood pressure can lead to posterior reversible encephalopathy syndromes. Special mention should be made of the "dialysis disequilibrium syndrome" resulting from rapid changes in urea and other osmolytes when dialysis is started under conditions of severe uremia. This can be minimised by starting dialysis at a lower rate, gradually increasing the duration of dialysis and using "simultaneous dialysis" strategies in high-risk patients. Electroencephalography (EEG) in these patients may reveal changes such as slower alpha rhythm and increased delta and theta waves. Triphasic sharp waves are considered to be specific indicators of metabolic complications.

Conclusions: neurological complications are thus common in patients with chronic kidney disease. Another set of manifestations may occur when these patients with CKD switch from dialysis to renal transplantation. Early detection of these manifestations may be vital to avoid long-term neurological consequences.

Literature:

1. Khodjaleva D. T., Khaydarova D. K. Clinical and neurophysiological characteristics of post-insular cognitive

disorders and issues of therapy optimization. Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. Dec.2019. P 82-86

2. Khamdamov B.Z. Indicators of immunocytocine status in purulent-necrotic lesions of the lower extremities in patients with diabetes mellitus.//American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences, 2020 10(7) 473-478 DOI: 10.5923/j.ajmm.2020.- 1007.08 10.

3. M. I. Kamalova, N.K.Khaidarov, Sh.E.Islamov, Pathomorphological Features of hemorrhagic brain strokes, Journal of Biomedicine and Practice 2020, Special issue, pp. 101-105

4. Kamalova Malika Ilkhomovna, Islamov Shavkat Eriyigitovich, Khaidarov Nodir Kadyrovich. Morphological Features Of Microvascular Tissue Of The Brain At Hemorrhagic Stroke. The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research, 2020. 2(10), 53-59

5. Khodjjeva D. T., Khaydarova D. K., Khaydarov N. K. Complex evaluation of clinical and instrumental data for justification of optive treatment activities in patients with resistant forms of epilepsy. American Journal of Research. USA. № 11-12, 2018. C.186-193.

